

Studies in the Cycloheptane Series. Part XXIX: Friedel-Crafts Reaction of the Anhydride of α,β -Diphenylglutaric Acid with Aromatic Hydrocarbons and Synthesis of Simple and Substituted Benz-2,3-diphenylcycloheptanes

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The anhydride of α,β -diphenylglutaric acid is condensed with benzene, toluene, three isomeric xylenes, chlorobenzene and tetralin in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride and the corresponding γ -substituted aroyl- α,β -diphenyl-*n*-butyric acids have been obtained. These on Clemmensen reduction furnish the respective δ -aryyl- α,β -diphenylvaleric acids which on cyclisation give the cyclic ketones. Clemmensen reduction of these give the simple and substituted benz-2,3-diphenylcycloheptanes.

α,β -Diphenylglutaric acid, m. p. 230-31°, obtained by the hydrolysis of diethyl- α,β -diphenylglutarate, was converted to its anhydride, m. p. 125°. The latter on hydrolysis afforded the lower melting isomer (208-10°), which has a trans-configuration¹ and no attempts were made to separate the optical enantiomers. The anhydride of this lower melting acid, which also had the m. p. 125°², on condensation with benzene, toluene, isomeric xylenes, and chlorobenzene under Friedel-Crafts reaction conditions gave the corresponding keto-acids^{3,4} (I: X=0). The structures of these were established by oxidation with sodium hypobromite to the known aromatic acids, m. ps. of which were undepressed by authentic samples.

Tetralin on similar condensation⁵ yielded only γ -2-(5,6,7,8-tetrahydronaphthoyl)- α,β -diphenyl-*n*-butyric acid (TLC).

Reduction of these keto-acids by modified Clemmensen method yielded the respective δ -aryyl- α,β -diphenylvaleric acids (I: X=H₂). The identities of the acids (I: X=0 and X=H₂) were confirmed through elemental analysis, equivalent weight and characterisation made through I. R. spectral

data and formation of S-benzylisothiuronium salts. The acids (I: X=0) gave doublets in the region 1690 cm⁻¹ and 1710 cm⁻¹ and acids (I: X=H₂) gave sharp peaks at 1690-1700 cm⁻¹. The acids (I: X=H₂) were cyclised with PPA to the corresponding cyclic ketones (II: Y=0), characterised through their 2,4-DNPs and I. R. data (1700 cm⁻¹). Subsequent Clemmensen reduction of these yielded the simple and substituted benz-2,3-diphenylcycloheptanes (II: Y=H₂).

Synthesis of benz-2,3-diphenylcycloheptane
 γ -Benzoyl- α,β -diphenyl-*n*-butyric acid (I: X=0)

Condensation of the anhydride (7.98 g; 0.03

TABLE-1
 γ -AROYL- α,β -DIPHENYL-*n*-BUTYRIC ACIDS

Aroyl	m. p. °C	Molecular formula	Percentage				S-Benzylisothiuronium salt m. p. °C
			Found		Requires		
			C	H	C	H	
1. 4-Methylbenzoyl	177	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₂	80.3	5.8	80.4	6.0	104
2. 3,4-Dimethylbenzoyl	174	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₂	80.5	6.4	80.6	6.4	110
3. 2,4 " "	149	"	80.3	6.2	80.6	6.4	112
4. 2,5 " "	194	"	80.6	6.3	80.6	6.4	106
5. 4-Chlorobenzoyl	152	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₂ Cl	72.8	4.8	73.0	5.0	137
6. 2-(5,6,7,8-Tetrahydronaphthoyl)	214	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ O ₂	81.3	6.5	81.4	6.5	122

mole) with dry benzene (35 ml) and powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (8.0 g; 0.06 mole) and working up the reaction mixture in the normal manner gave the keto-acid (I; X=O) (7.4 g; 71.8%), m. p. 145-6° from benzene-pet. ether. (Found : C, 79.8; H, 5.8; equiv., 343.8. $C_{23}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 80.0; H, 6.0%; equiv., 344.0-monobasic).

Its *S*-benzylisothiuronium salt (shining plates) had m. p. 122°.

Other substituted butyric acids were similarly obtained in 70-80% yield and are entered in Table 1.

δ-Phenyl- α , β -diphenylvaleric acid (I : X=H₂)

The above keto-acid (6.88 g; 0.02 mole) was reduced with zinc-amalgam (40 g) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (100 ml) (80 hr); on normal work up the acid (I; X=H₂) was obtained in fine needles from benzene and had m. p. 177°. (Yield : 4.4 g; 66.6%). (Found : C, 83.4; H, 6.4; equiv., 329.8. $C_{23}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 83.6; H, 6.4%; equiv., 330-monobasic).

Its *S*-benzylisothiuronium salt (fine needles) had m. p. 112°.

All the other substituted valeric acids were obtained in 60-70% yield and are given in Table 2.

6, 7-Benz-2, 3-diphenylcycloheptan-1-one (II : Y=O)

The above acid (3.3 g; 0.01 mole) was cyclised with PPA and the reaction product on working up gave the cyclic ketone (II : Y=O) from pet. ether (40-60°) in white cubes and had m. p. 164-5°, (Yield : 1.8 g; 61.3%).

(Found : C, 88.3; H, 6.3. $C_{23}H_{20}O$ requires C, 88.5; H, 6.4%).

Its 2, 4-DNP (cubes) had m. p. 233°.

All the other cyclic ketones similarly prepared in 60-65% yield are entered in Table 3.

6, 7-Benz-2, 3-diphenylcycloheptane

The above cyclic ketone (1.24 g; 0.004 mole) on reduction with amalgamated mossy zinc (20 g),

TABLE 2
 δ -ARYL- α , β -DIPHENYLVALERIC ACIDS

Aryl	m.p. °C	Mol. formula	Percentage				S-Benzylisothiuronium salt m.p. °C
			Found		Requires		
			C	H	C	H	
1. 4-Methylphenyl	202	$C_{24}H_{24}O_3$	83.9	6.9	84.0	7.0	107
2. 3, 4-Dimethylphenyl	214	$C_{25}H_{26}O_3$	83.7	6.8	83.8	7.0	124
3. 2, 4-	204	"	83.8	6.9	"	"	91
4. 2, 5-	208	"	83.7	6.8	"	"	164
5. 4-Chlorophenyl	201	$C_{23}H_{21}O_3Cl$	73.8	5.5	74.0	5.7	162
6. 2-(5, 6, 7, 8-tetrahydro-naphthyl)	213	$C_{27}H_{26}O_3$	84.2	7.1	84.3	7.3	104

TABLE 3
SUBSTITUTED BENZ-2, 3-DIPHENYLCYCLOHEPTAN-1-ONES

Substituents	m.p. °C	Mol. formula	Percentage				2, 4-DNP m.p. °C
			Found		Requires		
			C	H	C	H	
1. 8-Methylbenz	152	$C_{24}H_{22}O$	88.0	6.6	88.3	6.8	137
2. 7, 8-Dimethylbenz	165	$C_{25}H_{24}O$	88.1	8.2	88.2	8.4	230
3. 6, 8-	139	"	88.0	8.4	"	"	225
4. 6, 9-	112	"	88.1	8.3	"	"	141
5. 8-Chlorobenz	208	$C_{23}H_{19}OCl$	79.8	5.4	80.0	5.5	137
6. 7, 8-Tetramethylenebenz	270	$C_{27}H_{26}O$	88.4	6.9	88.5	7.1	141

TABLE 4
SUBSTITUTED BENZ-2, 3-DIPHENYLCYCLOHEPTANES

Substituents	m.p.	Mol. formula	Percentage			
			Found		Requires	
			C	H	C	H
1. 8-Methyl	148	$C_{24}H_{24}$	92.1	7.6	92.3	7.7
2. 7, 8-Dimethyl	201	$C_{25}H_{26}$	91.8	8.0	92.0	8.0
3. 6, 8-	137	"	91.9	7.9	"	"
4. 6, 9-	143	"	91.8	7.9	"	"
5. 8-Chloro	192	$C_{23}H_{21}Cl$	82.8	6.4	82.9	6.6
6. 7, 8-Tetramethylene	109	$C_{27}H_{26}$	91.8	7.9	92.0	8.0

concentrated hydrochloric acid (60 ml), toluene (1 ml) and glacial acetic acid (1 ml) (60 hr) furnished the hydrocarbon (II : $Y=H_2$) in fine cubes from benzene, m. p. 197° (Yield : 0.6 g ; 50%).

(Found : C, 92.4 ; H, 7.4. $C_{23}H_{22}$ requires C, 92.6 ; H, 7.4%.

All other hydrocarbons similarly prepared are entered in Table-4.

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